

INTERRELATION OF INFORMATION SECURITY INDICATORS AND QUALITY OF SERVICE IN DATA TRANSMISSION NETWORKS

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Abstract - with the intensive development of telecommunication infrastructure and integration into international networks, information security in data transmission networks is becoming increasingly relevant. However, at present, methods for quantitative assessment of information security in data transmission networks are lacking, even though such methods exist for most other quality of service indicators (accuracy, speed, and reliability). The integrity indicator, unlike traditional accuracy, takes into account the influence of both random and intentional security threats. This paper presents a simulation model for assessing security during random and intentional integrity violations and calculating the weight spectrum of cyclic redundancy codes.

Keywords - Information security, integrity, weight spectrum, error rate, cyclic code, packet loss.

INTRODUCTION

The intensive development of information infrastructure, based on high-speed data transmission systems (SPDs), has led to the emergence of a number of scientific problems, including those related to information security, which are among the most complex and knowledge-intensive. The introduction of new data transmission technologies requires a comprehensive approach to ensuring the information security of high-speed SPDs.

Information security in SPDs refers to the degree of protection of their information sphere from information security threats, leading to the deterioration of the specified qualitative characteristics of SPD operation, and thus causing harm to its users or owners.

The information sphere of SPD consists of:

- The informational resources of SPD (stored, processed, and transmitted data);

- The informational infrastructure (software, protocols, interfaces, procedures that support the functioning processes of the SPD, etc.).

The widespread use of foreign technologies and equipment in data transmission networks makes them particularly vulnerable to the use of information warfare. This is because the complex software used in these systems, whose source codes are not provided, makes systems and data transmission networks opaque to detailed monitoring. As a result, operators cannot know everything embedded in the equipment, which increases the likelihood of dangerous undocumented impacts, since the equipment and/or its software may include features that can be triggered by external commands or at a designated time.

In new international standards and recommendations from the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), and others, information security is considered as one of the quality of service indicators for data transmission networks. However, currently, there are no methods for the quantitative assessment of information security in telecommunications networks, although such methods are available for most other quality of service indicators (accuracy, speed, and reliability).

Let us consider the parameters that characterize the quality of operation of a data transmission network, which are divided into two groups. The first group includes parameters that characterize quality criteria such as speed, and the second group includes accuracy and reliability.

One of the most important accuracy criteria is the error rate. The degree of correspondence between the received and transmitted message is characterized by the concept of accuracy. A quantitative characteristic of accuracy is the error coefficient K_{error} , determined as the average number of errors n_{error} (incorrectly received elements) to the total number of elements n_{tran} transmitted during the test session.

$$K_{error} = \frac{n_{error}}{n_{tran}}$$

The main parameters characterizing QoS in IP networks are:

- packet transfer delay;
- packet delay variation (jitter);
- packet loss ratio;
- packet error ratio.

IP packet delivery parameters:

- IP packet transfer delay (IPTD);
- IP packet delay variation (IPDV);
- IP packet loss ratio (IPLR);
- IP packet error ratio (IPER).

Analysis shows that currently, information security in telecommunications networks does not have a quantitative assessment, whereas most other quality of service indicators (accuracy, speed, and reliability) do.

As a result, more attention is being paid to the task of ensuring the quality of telecommunications services in the presence of possible intentional and unintentional impacts on the transmitted user and control information. Therefore, the main goal of ensuring information security in telecommunications networks is to maintain such security characteristics as integrity and availability in the presence of intentional and unintentional threats to the information sphere.

In the ITU-T recommendations (X.800), the following definition is provided:

"Data integrity is an indicator that data has not been altered or destroyed in an unauthorized manner during transmission through communication systems (networks). Data (information) integrity means that the data is protected from unauthorized alteration, deletion, creation, and duplication, and that attempts to perform such unauthorized actions are indicated."

It should be noted that traditional quality parameters characterize the impact on service quality of random processes (noise, distortions, aging processes of devices and line structures, errors by operating personnel, and other causes), whereas information security parameters characterize intentional actions by malicious actors aimed at distorting the transmitted information, its destruction, and the introduction of false information.

To determine the possibility of violating information integrity in the presence of security threats, a simulation model is presented. The simulation model allows for simulating integrity violations under random and intentional threats and generating results. The attack on DTN (high-speed data transmission systems) is presented in Figure 1.

The algorithm for analyzing integrity control methods consists of:

- A random data string generator;
- An algorithm for calculating cyclic redundancy codes;

- A method for marking the transmitted message;
- A simulation of integrity violations under random and intentional security threats;
- A receiver part that determines the possibility of error undetection.

Fig. 1. Attack on DTN

The message marking method allows for the detection of malicious actions. If an attacker knows that the transmitted message is being checked for integrity using one of the integrity control algorithms, the integrity check for this message will include 4 extra bits (the marker), which, in turn, will be detected by the program during message analysis, as the program uses the integrity control calculation data without considering the last 4 bits. The format of the formed message is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. View of the Formed Message

A marker consisting of 4 bits is added to the message, calculated as the sum of every second bit of the data block. That is, if the message consists of 8 bits, then $M = 2\text{nd bit} + 4\text{th bit} + 6\text{th bit} + 8\text{th bit}$, where M is the marker.

Fig. 3. Simulation model for assessing security in the case of random integrity violations of information

Fig. 4. Simulation model for assessing security in the case of intentional integrity violations of information

The encoding methods discussed above were developed for conditions involving random interference on stored, processed, and transmitted information (data). In cases of intentional attacks, the discussed encoding methods should be used in conjunction with cryptographic transformation methods, creating

conditions where the best strategy for the attacker, for example, to introduce undetectable errors into the transmitted message, ensures the greatest benefit to the attacker.

Fig. 5. Simulation model for assessing security in the case of random integrity violations using cyclic redundancy code

Fig.6. Simulation model using the message marking method in the case of an intentional security threat

Simulation Modeling of Integrity Violation Threats Revealed the Following:

- In the case of random security threats, there is a 10-15% chance that undetected errors may occur in transmitted packets, which could lead to integrity violations. To reduce the probability, generating polynomials with higher code distances should be used—this is achieved by selecting polynomials of higher degree.
- In the case of intentional threats, the attacker may receive a packet, modify the data, and if they know the algorithm used for integrity checking, they could recalculate the cyclic redundancy code, so the error will not be detected upon reception.
- When using the message marking method, the probability of detecting errors significantly increases.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained in this work, the following conclusions can be made:

- To prevent an attacker from finding generating combinations, generating polynomials with higher code distances should be used. This can be achieved by introducing polynomials of higher degree.
- To prevent the extraction of a sequence from the array, two-level encryption using direct and reverse codes can be applied, which will eliminate the possibility of undetectable errors.
- The method of frequently changing the generating polynomial allows an attacker to determine the polynomial but prevents them from modifying it because a different polynomial will be in effect by the time of decryption. This allows an attacker to apply stream inversion and identify the location of the violated message.
- The method of changing the marker's position will not allow the attacker to mask data modifications as authentic because the changes will be incorrectly encrypted, as in the method with frequent changes in the generating polynomial.

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Anjuman sho‘basi

5. Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun’iy intellektning ahamiyati.